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SYNERGY «SCHOOL + UNIVERSITY»: NEW HORIZONS OF INTEGRATION OF EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMS

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Abstract. *Modern challenges associated with the digitalization of society, the formation of a knowledge economy and the growing demands for the universality of graduates' competencies call into question the effectiveness of the traditional model of separating school and university as two isolated educational environments. In conditions where the boundaries between levels of education are becoming increasingly conditional, there is a need to build synergetic trajectories that allow schoolchildren not only to acquire subject knowledge, but also to master the fundamental foundations of managerial, economic and philosophical culture.*

The article substantiates the concept of introducing modular courses in management, economics, philosophy and administration in a simplified form into the school curriculum using the pass/fail system, which eliminates the impact on academic performance. Such an organizational model allows minimizing stress traditionally associated with assessment procedures, and at the same time stimulates interest in self-determination, reflection and early professional orientation.

The scientific novelty of the study lies in the development of the "School-University 4.0" model, in which the integration of educational levels is understood not as a mechanical duplication of content, but as the creation of a cross-disciplinary environment for the formation of metacompetences - critical thinking, entrepreneurial outlook, the ability to manage projects and philosophical reflection. It is proposed to consider this model as a strategic tool for building "bridges" between general and higher education, reducing the "transition shock" and helping to prepare students for the intellectual and professional challenges of the 21st century.

In practical terms, the article reveals the prospects for using the credit system within the framework of integrative disciplines, demonstrates its advantages for educational motivation and social maturity of schoolchildren, and also examines international analogues of pre-college programs (Advanced Placement , International Baccalaureate , Foundation Year) with their adaptation to local conditions. Thus, the synergy of "school + university" is positioned not only as an innovative educational experiment, but also as a necessary step towards the formation of an educational ecosystem capable of preparing individuals of the future - flexible, creative and ready for interdisciplinary challenges.

Keywords: *synergy of education, pre-college, soft skills, metacompetences, pass/fail, school-university, philosophy of education.*

In the context of rapid digitalization and globalization, educational systems are faced with the need to rethink their structure and content. The traditional model, in which school and university exist

as autonomous units, no longer meets the challenges of the 21st century. At the junction of eras, a new educational paradigm is being formed, where the key factors are not so much subject knowledge as the ability for interdisciplinary thinking, managing one's own development trajectory and adapting to rapidly changing socio-economic conditions.

School education today is focused primarily on mastering basic academic disciplines, while university requires applicants to be prepared for independent work, research, and strategic choice of professional specialization. The gap between these two stages manifests itself in the “transition shock” — the psychological and cognitive stress experienced by school graduates when faced with a new paradigm of academic freedom and a high degree of responsibility for learning outcomes.

Overcoming this gap is possible through the introduction of synergetic educational models that combine elements of the school and university programs. Of particular importance in this process are the meta-level disciplines - management, economics, philosophy, management fundamentals, which are integrated into high school not as a mandatory and assessment-laden block, but as a space for trials, self-determination and the formation of a broad worldview horizon.

The fundamental idea is that such courses should be modular and simplified and assessed on a pass/fail basis. Such a system removes the threat of a decline in academic performance and at the same time allows schoolchildren to “try on” the university culture of learning: mastering the conceptual apparatus, participating in discussions, and project work. This not only promotes the development of soft skills and critical thinking, but also allows you to build individual educational trajectories, where the choice of a future profession will be the result of conscious and conscious reflection, and not external pressure.

International experience confirms the potential of such models. Advanced programs Placement (USA), International Baccalaureate (Europe), Foundation Year (Great Britain and Australia) have already proven the effectiveness of the early introduction of university practices into school education. However, the proposed model "School-University 4.0" is distinguished by an innovative emphasis on reducing assessment pressure and turning interdisciplinary courses into a tool for developing metacompetences, rather than an additional source of workload [1]. Thus, the introduction of such modular disciplines opens up prospects for the formation of a new generation educational ecosystem, where school and university exist not as sequential, but as complementary stages, ensuring the continuity of personal and intellectual development.

The idea of continuity of education has deep historical and philosophical roots and has always been considered one of the key principles of building a holistic educational system. Even Jan Amos Komensky in his "Great Didactics" emphasized the need for a "natural transition" between stages of education, where each subsequent one does not cancel the previous one, but develops it and brings it to a new level of understanding. This principle became the basis for the formation of educational doctrines of the New Age, where education was thought of as a process of continuous and progressive development of the individual.

In the 19th–20th centuries, the concept of continuity was reinforced in the works of J. Dewey, J.-J. Rousseau, and later by L.S. Vygotsky, who pointed out the importance of the “zone of proximal development” as a pedagogical mechanism for the smooth transition of a student from the acquired level of knowledge to more complex forms of activity [3–5]. Thus, continuity in education is considered not only as an organizational principle, but also as a psychological and pedagogical law that ensures harmony between age stages, cognitive capabilities, and the requirements of the educational environment.

Modern concepts of sustainable development and knowledge economy have given this principle a new meaning. In the context of rapid changes, educational continuity should ensure not only academic consistency of programs, but also metacompetence coherence: the formation of skills in schoolchildren that will be in demand in the university and professional environment. At the same time, we are not talking about formal duplication of content, but about the creation of “through educational lines” that allow learning to be perceived as a continuous trajectory - from basic school to professional training and subsequent self-education [1].

In this logic, the integration of university course elements into school education can be seen as a modern embodiment of the principle of continuity. It forms a bridge between the two levels of the educational system and provides cognitive, cultural and social preparation for future challenges. Unlike the classical model, where the transition between school and university is often “fragmentary”, the proposed synergy allows for a softer and more conscious trajectory that eliminates the risks of an adaptation crisis.

Thus, the concept of continuity in education is currently being transformed from the idea of a smooth transition between stages into a strategy for the formation of a continuous educational ecosystem, where school and university education are not opposed, but interact, creating conditions for sustainable personal development.

In global educational practice, there has long been a tendency to “blur the boundaries” between secondary and higher education. Universities in a number of countries act not only as institutions of professional training, but also as partners in the process of forming an academic culture in high school students. This approach is implemented through pre-college programs aimed at providing students with the opportunity for early introduction to the university environment, mastering key concepts of future disciplines and developing research skills.

One of the most famous examples is the Advanced system Placement (AP) in the USA. It provides schoolchildren with access to university-level courses with subsequent credit for admission. The key result of participation in AP is not so much a quantitative increase in knowledge, but a qualitative change in thinking: students master the basics of academic discussion, project work and analytical work, which form the core of university culture [6-8].

In Europe, the most important analogue is the International Baccalaureate (IB Diploma) program. Programme). It focuses not only on subject knowledge, but also on the development of critical thinking, intercultural communication and research activity. The IB system has become a universal “bridge” between school and university, especially in countries where mobility and international academic integration are in demand [9-13].

In the UK and Australia, so-called Foundations are common Year — preparatory courses at universities that allow schoolchildren to “immerse themselves” in the academic environment and master basic disciplines before starting full-time education. At the same time, the main task remains to reduce the adaptation barrier and develop stable skills in schoolchildren for working with large amounts of information, academic writing, and project research [14-16].

In Kazakhstan and a number of CIS countries, pre-university colleges and lyceums at universities are actively developing, creating conditions for early profiling. However, unlike Western models, they are often focused on formal strengthening of subject training, rather than on the formation of metacompetences, which limits their synergetic potential [1,17,18].

Comparative analysis shows that the most successful pre-college programs are based on three principles: A gentle introduction to the university environment through simplified courses, project work and academic internships. Minimizing assessment pressure - using a pass/fail format or a comprehensive portfolio assessment. Focus on meta-competencies – development of analytical thinking, research culture and knowledge management skills [1]. Thus, international experience demonstrates that the university as an early start space is becoming not a tool for “accelerating” learning, but a mechanism for preparing a mature, conscious and motivated student. For Kazakhstan and the post-Soviet space, this direction opens up the possibility of modernizing the education system by introducing hybrid forms of interaction between school and university, focused not only on the academic, but also on the personal and professional readiness of students [17,18].

The philosophy of education has traditionally viewed school and university as two qualitatively different stages of personality development. School acts as a space for socialization and basic personality development, where the foundations of worldview, values, and cognitive structures are laid. University, on the contrary, symbolizes the stage of personality development, its intellectual and professional autonomy. The synergy of these two levels presupposes the creation of a model where

school and university cease to be isolated, but turn into interconnected links in a single educational cycle.

From the standpoint of the philosophy of education, school can be understood as an "anthropological matrix" where the individual receives his first ideas about the world, society and himself. Here, not only the transmission of knowledge is important, but also the development of abilities for critical understanding of reality. The university, on the contrary, embodies a space of intellectual freedom, where the individual goes beyond ready-made schemes and begins to construct his own research and professional trajectory.

In the synergetic model, education is conceived as a process of continuous self-development, where school and university form a dialectical unity: the former provides the basis for a holistic perception of the world, while the latter reveals potential in project, research and practical activities. That is why the introduction of university modules into school education should not be perceived as "accelerated maturation," but as a way to expand the horizon of students' self-identification.

From a philosophical point of view, the synergy of these stages reflects the principle of "horizontal integration of knowledge", where the humanities, social and management disciplines cease to be an attribute of exclusively university education. Their simplified introduction into high school through the pass/fail format becomes a tool for preparing for future choice and the formation of a reflexive attitude to knowledge. Thus, the student's personality gradually emerges from the state of "an object of pedagogical influence" and begins to become a subject of his own educational path.

1. The synergetic philosophy of "school + university" is integrated into the global context of Illich's ideas I., Delors J., Freire P, who viewed education as a practice of freedom, creativity and critical reflection. In this logic, the university ceases to be the "beginning of adult life" and becomes its natural continuation, while the school turns from a "dressing room" into a full-fledged space for early personality development [8,12,19]. Thus, the philosophy of synergy demonstrates that only by combining two stages – school and university – is it possible to form a holistic, mature and innovatively thinking individual, capable of productive participation in the life of the knowledge society.

In the context of the transformation of education towards interdisciplinarity and a competence-based approach, disciplines traditionally related to the university level are becoming increasingly important: management, economics, philosophy and the basics of management. Their early introduction into the school curriculum in the format of modules does not pursue the goal of "academic deepening", but serves a strategic task - preparing students for a conscious perception of future university experience and the formation of metacompetences in demand in the digital age [1].

The modular principle is of key importance here. Unlike the linear subjects of the school curriculum, modules are built according to flexible logic: short blocks (6-8 lessons) focused on the practical application of knowledge and the development of skills. This approach removes the barriers of "overload" of the program and allows integrating new disciplines into the existing curriculum without compromising the basic subjects. Management in the school format can be presented as "management of everyday projects": organizing group work, time management, planning tasks. Students gain experience in structuring actions and making decisions - universal skills that go beyond specific professions. The economy is understood through the "microeconomics of everyday life" – understanding resources, the value of labor, the basics of financial literacy, and the logic of economic choice. This module forms the basic ability for economic thinking, which is necessary for orientation in a world of rapid change. Philosophy is taught in a practical way - as the development of critical and reflective thinking skills. This is not an academic history of philosophy, but the ability to ask questions, analyze arguments, and see alternatives. Thus, philosophy becomes an instrument of intellectual freedom and responsibility. Management can be integrated through the study of the "fundamentals of leadership and self-organization": teamwork, role distribution, decision-making under uncertainty. Here, the prerequisites for the formation of future managers, entrepreneurs, and leaders of public initiatives are laid.

The introduction of such modules into school practice should be accompanied by new pedagogical technologies: case method, game simulations, project assignments, debates. This will allow us to move away from the reproductive approach and focus on activity-based learning, where knowledge is born in the process of interaction, and not through memorization.

Thus, modular courses become an "entry point" into university culture, allowing schoolchildren to safely try out new formats of working with information and group dynamics. This not only reduces the future adaptation barrier, but also forms a generation of graduates ready to make a conscious choice of educational and professional trajectory.

One of the most controversial issues of introducing new subjects into the school curriculum is the problem of assessment pressure. The traditional grading system (from "2" to "5" or its analogues) historically served as a motivation and control function, but in modern conditions it is increasingly becoming a source of stress, demotivation and formal acquisition of knowledge. This is especially noticeable in cases where students have to master new and unfamiliar subjects that go beyond their basic educational experience.

The pass/fail format is being integrated into the educational process as a fundamentally different assessment model. It assumes a minimum threshold of requirements (for example, attending classes, participating in discussions, completing practical assignments), after which the student receives a pass. The absence of a traditional grading of grades eliminates situations of "race for points", turning learning into a space of experimentation and search, rather than coercion.

The advantages of this approach are obvious: students are not afraid of "getting a low grade", which stimulates creativity and boldness in statements; attention is focused on the process of acquiring knowledge, and not on the final grade on the report card; many foreign universities (especially in the USA and Scandinavia) use the pass /fail system in the first years for a smooth adaptation of students. Thus, its implementation in schools prepares for the future educational format; since management, economics and philosophy are not mandatory examination subjects at school, the pass/fail assessment allows them to be integrated without the risk of reducing overall academic performance; the student is assessed by involvement and ability to practically apply knowledge, and not by formal reproduction of the material.

In addition, the use of the "pass/fail" system corresponds to the trends of competency-based and humanistic education, where the key factors are not formal indicators, but the development of meta-competencies – the ability to think critically, work in a team, and make decisions.

Thus, the format of the credit system acts as an innovative tool for reducing academic pressure and, at the same time, a pedagogical strategy for supporting freedom of choice. In combination with the modular principle, it allows new disciplines to be transformed into a space for free search, while maintaining academic discipline and responsibility.

Modern educational systems are increasingly faced with the need to prepare graduates not only to pass exams and enter university, but also to live in conditions of uncertainty and rapid change in the socio-economic environment. In this regard, metacompetences are becoming a key reference point-supra-subject abilities that allow integrating knowledge, skills and personal qualities to solve complex problems [1].

Philosophy as a modular course opens up space for the formation of a culture of questions, analysis of arguments and verification of facts. In conditions of information overload, it is the ability to critically select, structure and interpret information that becomes the foundation of intellectual maturity. In a school environment, this can be realized through debates, essays, role-playing games and case studies that stimulate dialogic thinking.

Management and economics in the school format allow developing basic communication skills, teamwork and presentation of ideas. These skills - negotiation, reasoned expression of a position, teamwork - form the basis for future success both at university and in the professional environment. It is important that the development of soft skills at school reduces the risk of socio-psychological maladjustment of students in the first years of study at a university.

The course "Fundamentals of Management" is integrated into the educational process as a leadership laboratory. Students try themselves in the roles of organizers of group projects, facilitators of discussions or moderators of school events. Here, responsibility for the result, the ability to coordinate resources and strategic planning skills are formed—qualities that become the core of future management and entrepreneurial activity.

The synergy of management, economics and philosophy opens up opportunities for integrating knowledge at the intersection of the humanities and applied fields. This forms in schoolchildren an understanding of the interrelationship between disciplines and teaches them to see the complexity of social processes. This approach corresponds to the trends of STEAM education (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, Mathematics), where the emphasis is on interdisciplinary projects and practice-oriented learning.

One of the key challenges in integrating university modules into school education is the risk of overloading the curriculum. Modern schoolchildren are already faced with a highly intensive educational process: the expansion of the list of compulsory subjects, preparation for national exams, participation in Olympiads and extracurricular activities create a situation of constant cognitive stress. The introduction of additional disciplines, even in a simplified format, can be perceived by students and their parents as another source of pressure.

A study in the field of educational psychology [14] shows that excessive workload reduces not only motivation, but also the efficiency of knowledge acquisition: students tend to memorize superficially, avoid creative forms of activity, and demonstrate an increase in anxiety. For school education, this is fraught with the formation of a “saturation effect,” in which any new content is perceived as excessive and unnecessary.

However, the very idea of synergy between school and university does not imply a mechanical increase in teaching hours. On the contrary, modular courses should be built into the existing program according to the principle of flexible adaptation: use of the variable part of the curriculum; integration into project activities and elective courses; replacing excessive formal reproductive classes with activity-based formats (cases, debates, group projects). In addition, it is important to emphasize that the proposed courses are of a metacompetence nature, which means that their content may partially overlap with tasks already being solved within related disciplines. For example, the development of critical thinking is possible simultaneously in philosophy and literature classes, and project assignments on management can be integrated with computer science or social studies courses [1]. Thus, the key task of educational administrators is to ensure that new courses do not formally increase the workload, but transform it qualitatively, creating conditions for more conscious, active and interdisciplinary learning. Otherwise, the innovative idea risks becoming a source of resistance from students, parents and teachers, which will neutralize its strategic potential.

One of the most predictable and at the same time systemic barriers to the implementation of the synergetic model of "school + university" is resistance to the traditional assessment system. The very logic of domestic and post-Soviet education is historically based on quantitative indicators: grades, ratings, average scores, which are perceived as a universal and objective tool for measuring the success of a student. In this paradigm, the teacher, parent and government agencies rely on the grade as the main marker of the quality of education.

pass/fail format undermines the traditional foundations of this system. Resistance is strengthened by the fact that assessment in the traditional system performs not only an academic but also a social-normative function: the mark becomes an instrument of disciplinary control, a way of managing motivation and a form of social comparison. The rejection of the usual scales means the need to find new instruments for recording and recognizing academic achievements, which requires both methodological and organizational changes.

However, international experience (for example, the use of the pass /fail system in universities in the USA, Canada, and Finland) shows that abandoning strict point differentiation does not lead to a decrease in the quality of training. On the contrary, it encourages students to participate in the educational process for the sake of the experience itself and the development of competencies, and

not for the sake of assessment. Moreover, studies demonstrate that the pass/fail system helps reduce anxiety and academic stress, while maintaining responsibility for meeting minimum requirements.

For Kazakhstan and the post-Soviet space, the implementation of such a model will require a gradual transition: parallel use of traditional assessment and the pass/fail format in different blocks of the program; development of transparent criteria for receiving credit (participation, completion of practical assignments, project activity); active work with parents and teachers to explain the goals and advantages of the new system. Thus, resistance to the traditional assessment system is a natural manifestation of institutional inertia. It can be overcome only through a systemic dialogue between the school, university, government structures and society. Otherwise, any innovation risks remaining a formal superstructure that does not change the essence of the educational process.

One of the most important advantages of integrating university modules into school education is smoothing the transition from school to higher education. For most graduates, this stage is accompanied by a phenomenon called "transition shock" in pedagogical literature. It manifests itself in a sharp change in the educational paradigm: from an environment where learning is based on detailed regulation and control by the teacher, the student enters a university where independence, the ability to self-manage and a proactive attitude towards knowledge are expected of him.

As a result, many first-year students face difficulties: inability to manage time and resources; lack of habit of independent reading and research work; stress from new formats (lectures, seminars, discussions, project assignments); cognitive and emotional overload. The introduction of modular courses in management, economics, philosophy and administration in schools can significantly soften this barrier. International studies (in particular, the practice of pre-college courses in the USA and Europe) show that such programs reduce the level of anxiety of first-year students, increase their academic success and accelerate socialization in the university environment. For Kazakhstan and the post-Soviet countries, this effect is of particular importance, since the gap between school and university is historically large: school remains more directive, while the university makes demands on autonomy.

Thus, the introduction of university modules in senior classes serves as a "soft springboard", allowing graduates not just to adapt, but to come to university with experience in academic communication, self-organization skills, and an understanding of the value of interdisciplinary knowledge. This not only reduces the percentage of unsuccessful students in the first years, but also contributes to the formation of a sustainable motivation for lifelong learning.

One of the central effects of the introduction of modular university courses into school education is a significant increase in academic motivation and the formation of a more conscious attitude among high school students towards the choice of a future profession.

The traditional school curriculum, focused on mastering basic subjects, is often perceived by students as being disconnected from real life and professional prospects. As a result, interest in learning decreases: knowledge is acquired formally, and the process of preparing for final exams becomes mechanical. The introduction of courses in management, economics, philosophy and administration changes the educational optics, creating space for a direct connection between knowledge and life.

International experience confirms this trend. In countries where pre-college programs are developed, the level of student satisfaction with their educational choice is significantly higher, and the percentage of students changing their course of study in the first years is lower. For Kazakhstan, this means a strategic step towards the formation of a conscious applicant who comes to the university not by chance, but with an understanding of his own interests and goals.

One of the most strategic effects of introducing university modules into school education is the opportunity to accelerate the formation of the "university of the future" model. In the classical paradigm, a university is thought of as a space where a person gets only after finishing school and successfully passing entrance exams. However, in the context of digitalization, global competition and the knowledge economy, a university is no longer exclusively an institution of higher education

and is gradually turning into an ecosystem of continuous learning, to which a person connects much earlier and remains a part of it throughout his or her life.

The integration of management, economics, philosophy and administration courses into the school curriculum — even in a simplified format and on a pass/fail system — effectively turns the school into a “pre-university laboratory.” Here, students receive not only basic knowledge, but also experience in mastering academic practices: participating in discussions, conducting project research, presenting results, and teamwork. These formats are integrated into the school ecosystem, creating an environment where students are both schoolchildren and potential students.

Thus, the university of the future is formed not as a closed institution, but as an open network, covering school, college, university and the system of additional education. In this model, the school plays the role of an “entry point” into the academic community, and the university is a space for deepening and developing already formed skills.

It is important to emphasize that such integration contributes to the formation of a new type of educational identity: the student begins to perceive himself not as an object of pedagogical influence, but as a subject of his own educational path, included in a broader ecosystem of knowledge. This creates the prerequisites for the formation of a lifelong culture learning (lifelong learning), where the university becomes not the final stage, but a permanent partner of the individual.

In addition, the synergy between school and university opens up opportunities for digital transformation of education: the use of online university courses (MOOC), blended learning formats, virtual laboratories and simulators. The school becomes a platform for testing these solutions, and the university becomes a center for their methodological support and development.

The introduction of modular courses in management, economics, philosophy and administration into the school curriculum requires not only methodological but also technological support. Here, artificial intelligence (AI) can play a key role, acting as a tool for personalization, adaptation and expansion of the educational experience. Unlike traditional methods, where the teacher is the main source of information, AI allows for the construction of a hybrid model in which the student gains access to multi-layered educational resources, interacts with digital mentors and forms an individual development trajectory [20]. The use of AI in modular courses serves a triple function: personalizes learning ; immersively simulates the university environment; provides the teacher with digital analytics .

Modern education is increasingly shifting from the transfer of subject knowledge to the formation of metacompetences — universal abilities that allow graduates to act effectively in conditions of uncertainty, digitalization, and global competition. In this process, artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming not just an automation tool, but a digital simulator of future experience that models situations that require critical analysis, creativity, communication, and leadership.

In the classical sense, a university is a “place” where you go after school. In the logic of the AI ecosystem, it becomes a process that begins at school, continues at the university, and is transformed into a lifelong system. learning. This university of the future unites schools, digital platforms, research centers and the labor market into a single smart network, where AI manages information flows, personalizes content and ensures the continuity of the educational trajectory.

Thus, the “university of the future” ceases to be an institution, but becomes a living AI ecosystem, which a student enters even before enrollment and remains a part of throughout his or her life. This not only reduces the transition barrier, but also forms a new type of educational culture, where learning is perceived as a continuous, personalized and interdisciplinary process.

The modern education system faces the need to bridge the gap between school and university. The traditional model, where these stages existed as isolated worlds, no longer meets the requirements of the knowledge economy and the digital age. The integration of modular courses in management, economics, philosophy and administration into senior grades of school in the pass/fail format is becoming not only a pedagogical innovation, but also a strategic tool for forming a holistic educational trajectory.

The synergy of “school + university” allows: smooth out the barrier of transition to a university and reduce the stress of adaptation; to form internal motivation and ensure a conscious choice of profession; develop key metacompetencies - critical thinking, soft skills, leadership and cross-disciplinarity; transform the school from a “university dressing room” into a laboratory of early experience, where individuals receive the first tools for independently constructing their educational and professional path.

Artificial intelligence is of particular importance in this model. It acts as a catalyst for synergy, providing personalization of learning, support for the pass/fail system, development of metacompetencies, and the formation of the university ecosystem of the future as a distributed digital network. At the same time, it is AI that is capable of turning education into a process of continuous and adaptive growth, where the school becomes the entry point, and the university is a space for disclosure and deepening, while maintaining a single digital identity of the student.

However, the implementation of such solutions requires attention to ethical and organizational challenges: data protection, overcoming digital inequality, training teachers and preserving the humanistic dimension of education. Only in the balance of technologies and values is sustainable transformation possible, capable of ensuring the competitiveness and cultural maturity of future generations.

Thus, the synergy of school, university and artificial intelligence forms a new paradigm of education, where learning ceases to be linear and fragmented. It becomes continuous, integrated and future-oriented, creating a generation of individuals who are ready not only to adapt to changes, but also to actively initiate them.

Project "Synergy school No. 11 - KarIU Temirtau"

General concept

Creation of a pilot program integrating senior classes of School No. 11 and Karaganda Industrial University (KaRIU). The goal is to build a bridge between secondary and higher education through modular courses in economics, management, philosophy, administration and digital technologies. The training is based on the “pass/fail” principle to relieve the stress of grades and focus on the development of metacompetencies.

Project objectives

The goal of the project "Synergy School No. 11 - KarIU Temirtau" is to create an integrated educational model that ensures a smooth transition of students from school to university level of preparation through the introduction of modular courses in management, economics, philosophy and administration using digital technologies and artificial intelligence.

The project aims to:

1. Reducing the adaptation barrier between school and university by introducing schoolchildren to academic practices and digital learning tools early on.

2. Formation of new generation meta-competencies - critical thinking, communication, leadership, project approach, digital literacy - which will become the foundation for successful mastering of university programs.

3. Increasing student motivation through the integration of practice-oriented modules related to real economic, managerial and social situations.

4. To prepare conscious applicants to KarIU who make their choice of profession not by chance, but based on personal interests, abilities and prior experience of participating in university projects.

5. Development of a new pedagogical model at the intersection of school and university, where teachers and lecturers of KarIU act as mentors and facilitators, and artificial intelligence ensures personalization and transparency of learning.

6. Creation of an educational ecosystem in Temirtau, where schools, universities and industrial enterprises act as interconnected links in the training of personnel for the region.

Thus, the goal of the project goes beyond simple preparation for admission: it forms a sustainable system of educational continuity, where the school becomes the entry point into the

university culture, and KUU becomes the center of personal development and professional orientation already at the senior stages of school education.

Implementation format

The project "Synergy School No. 11 - KarIU Temirtau" is implemented in the format of a pilot integrated educational program based on a combination of school and university practices. Its key principle is modularity, variability and personalization of training with the active use of artificial intelligence technologies.

The main forms of implementation include:

1. Modular courses

Courses in management, economics, philosophy and administration in grades 10–11.

They are built according to block -modular logic (6–8 weeks), which allows them to be integrated into the curriculum without overload.

The assessment system is **pass /fail**, stress-free and focused on participation and engagement.

2. Team teaching

Lessons are taught in a collaborative format between school teachers and KarIU instructors.

University teachers give introductory lectures and master classes, school teachers help to adapt the material.

A unified educational community is being formed, where students feel like they are part of the university culture.

3. University internships for schoolchildren

Excursions and laboratory classes at KarIU (virtual and in-person).

Participation of schoolchildren in scientific and practical conferences, debates and hackathons organized by the university.

Project groups of “schoolchildren + students” to solve real cases (for example, on urban infrastructure, ecology or digital services).

4. Digitalization and AI

Using chatbots and intelligent tutors for consultations and knowledge testing.

Personalized learning through adaptive platforms: the system selects tasks depending on the level of preparation.

Formation of a student's digital portfolio, which accompanies him from the 10th grade and is taken into account when entering KarIU .

5. Extracurricular formats

School and university clubs of interest (economics, philosophy, management, engineering).

Case studies and business games (for example, “School Startup”, “Mini-City of the Future”).

Summer schools and winter camps at KarIU for schoolchildren with an emphasis on project work.

6. Hybrid learning

Some modules are implemented online (lectures by KarIU , recordings of webinars).

Some are offline, with an emphasis on collaborative activities.

A unified digital educational environment is being formed, accessible to both school students and KarIU students .

7. Industry Connection

Connecting Temirtau industrial partners to the project (JSC Qarmet, machine-building enterprises).

Joint mini-projects of schoolchildren and students based on requests from enterprises.

Primary professional experience for schoolchildren through participation in practice-oriented tasks.

Thus, the implementation form is built as a multi-level interaction model: the school gets access to university resources and AI tools, KAIU gets motivated applicants, and the region gets trained young specialists with experience in project work even before entering the university.

Stages of implementation

Phase I (2025–2026): Preparatory

Joint development of modules by school No. 11 and KarIU .

Advanced training for school teachers (courses at KarIU).

Creation of a pilot AI assistant to support students and schoolchildren.

Phase II (2026–2027): pilot

Launch of modules in 10th grade.

Conducting the first joint classes at the KarIU .

Formation of digital portfolios of students.

Phase III (2027–2028): Expansion

Connecting 11th graders.

Creation of school and student project teams.

Conducting a regional scientific and practical conference "School and University without Borders".

Stage IV (from 2028): integration

Automatic accounting of school credits upon admission to KarIU.

Creation of the Center for Continuity of Education "School- KarIU".

Connecting other schools in Temirtau to the model.

Expected results

The implementation of the project will achieve significant educational, organizational and socio-economic effects at the level of the school, university and the city of Temirtau.

1. For schoolchildren

Reducing the adaptation barrier when transferring to university: graduates of school No. 11 will come to KarIU with experience of working in university formats (lectures, seminars, project assignments).

Formation of meta-competencies (critical thinking, teamwork, leadership, digital literacy) that complement subject knowledge.

Increased motivation for learning: schoolchildren will see a direct connection between knowledge and future professions.

Conscious choice of educational trajectory: reducing the number of cases when students change their specialty after the first year.

A digital portfolio of each graduate, containing achievements and projects, useful for admission and career start.

2. For school No. 11

Strengthening the status of an innovative school in the region implementing a pre-university training model.

Improving the quality of the educational process through the introduction of new disciplines and technologies.

Improving the image among parents and applicants: the school will be perceived as a launching pad for admission to KGIU.

Methodological development of teachers: teachers will gain experience working in a team with university professors and master new teaching roles (facilitator, mentor, coach).

3. For KAIU Temirtau

An influx of motivated applicants who are already familiar with the university environment and ready for independent study.

Reducing the percentage of maladjustment and academic failure among first-year students.

Formation of an educational brand: KGIU will become a center of innovation and digital practices, open to the school and the city.

Integration into the regional ecosystem: the university will be perceived not as a “separate institution”, but as an active participant in the school and city community.

4. For the city and region

Connection between education and industry: school and student projects will solve practical problems of the city (infrastructure, ecology, digitalization).

Building social capital: creating a new generation of citizens with critical thinking and leadership skills.

Reducing the outflow of young people: applicants will see prospects in KarIU and Temirtau, which will strengthen the local personnel base.

Creating a model that can be scaled up to other schools and universities in the region.

Thus, the project “Synergy School No. 11 – KarIU Temirtau” will have a multi-level effect: from improving the quality of school education and the competitiveness of KarIU to strengthening the regional system of personnel training.

Development Prospects

The project has significant potential for expansion and institutionalization, going beyond the local initiative of School No. 11 and KarIU. Its further development can be implemented in several strategic directions:

1. Scaling to the city and region

Connecting other schools in Temirtau to the project and forming a network of partner schools of KarIU .

Creation of a “school-university cluster” in the Karaganda region, where KarIU acts as a methodological and digital integration center.

Conducting annual city educational forums “School + University”, where projects of schoolchildren and students are presented.

2. Integration with industrial enterprises

Involvement of industrial partners of the region (Qarmet, mechanical engineering enterprises, IT companies) in the organization of practice-oriented cases.

Creation of “ mini-orders” for school and student teams, where real production tasks are adapted to the level of 10-11 grades.

Formation of a system of “early dual education”: schoolchildren become familiar not only with the university, but also with the industry.

3. Digital transformation

Development of the AI platform: transition from a chatbot to a smart educational assistant that accompanies schoolchildren and students throughout their entire journey.

Creation of a single digital portfolio database, which is automatically integrated into the KGIU system upon admission.

Implementation of virtual laboratories and simulators for modular courses (economic games, engineering simulations, management simulators).

4. Academic institutionalization

Development of the official program “Pre-college KarIU”, approved by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Inclusion of modules in the system of elective disciplines in senior schools.

Preparation of joint publications and methodological materials (school + KarIU) for the exchange of experience at the level of Kazakhstan.

5. International cooperation

Connecting the Kar IU and schools in the region to the Erasmus + and UNESCO Education 2030 programs, where the integration of schools and universities is one of the priorities.

Creation of network projects with foreign universities (online courses, joint hackathons).

Formation of “virtual classes” where Temirtau schoolchildren will be able to work in a team with foreign students.

6. Long-term effect

Preparing a new generation of applicants focused on engineering, economics and management professions.

Reducing the educational and social gap between school and university.

Transformation of KarIU into a regional center for innovation in education, forming a personnel base for the industrial development of Temirtau and the region.

Thus, the project's prospects are to transform a local initiative into a systemic solution for the region, and in the future – into a model that can be scaled up at the national level as a “Kazakhstani pre-college integration format”.

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